
Motivational Ability of Teachers and Parental Involvement in Motivation as Correlates of Personality Development among Kindergarten Pupils

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ABSTRACT: The study was conducted to determine the relationship of teachers' motivational ability and parents' involvement in motivation with that of the aspects of personality development among kindergarten pupils. This study involves 34 kindergarten teachers and 175 parents from schools in the District of Nagcarlan, Division of Laguna during the school year 2022- 2023. It utilizes descriptive correlational design, and convenience sampling design in gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data. The study utilized a survey questionnaire using Likert Scale of 1- 5 in perceiving the major variables of the study. Correlation results reveal that there is no significant relationship shown between motivational techniques to expressive development ($r=0.094$), and socio-emotional development ($r=0.077$) while there is a significant relationship in instructional incentives to fine motor development ($r=0.156$) and cognitive development ($r=0.152$). Moreover, there is no significant relationship shown between social interaction to expressive development ($r=0.118$), cognitive development ($r=0.09$), and socio-emotional development ($r=0.121$) while there is a significant relationship in social interaction to fine motor development ($r=0.171$). The study recommends expanding with a longer timeframe and consist of a larger sample size, and with the added perspective from different schools or grade level as well and use other variables to identify the advantages and disadvantages of motivational ability of teachers and parents' involvement in motivation in relation to the development of personality among kindergarten pupils. Another study that focus on the challenges faced by the teacher and parents towards and aspects of personality development of kindergarten pupils maybe conducted.

KEYWORDS: Kindergarten Pupils, Personality Development, Motivational Ability, Involvement in Motivation

I. INTRODUCTION

Pre-kindergarten and early childhood education is the foundation and basis for learning and development. The most recent issue concerning education was the implementation of Kindergarten or the so-called Early Childhood Education. As decade ago, preschools had been established by private entities which catered to children's parents who can afford to pay the fees for the purposes of aiding the child in his/her mental growth and physical development. However, today early childhood education today is no longer an occasional preschool offering, but is now compulsory in the public schools.

Teachers and parents frequently find themselves frustrated with their children wondering how to motivate them to try harder on school work. Teachers and parents should find different strategies on how to motivate the kindergarten pupils. Specially in this time that children had no idea about schooling because of the pandemic.

Pupils' motivation affects every aspect of school life, from attendance to academic performance to extra-curricular activities. Promoting the greatest motivation possible is extremely important for every teacher in K-12 especially in today's educational climate, where schools are continuously under pressure to improve test scores, responsibility and accountability. The motivational ability of teachers and parental involvement may have a positive impact on the temperament, environment, and character of kindergarten pupils. It may have an impact on the personality development of the pupil which is ever changing and subject to contextual factors and life-altering experience.

Personality development of the child is the development of the organized pattern of behaviors and attitudes that makes him distinctive. Personality development occurs by the ongoing interaction of temperament, character, and environment. Personality is what makes him a unique person, and it is recognizable soon after birth. A child's personality has several components: temperament, environment, and character. Temperament is the set of genetically determined traits that determine the child's approach to the world and how the child learns about the world. There are no genes that specify personality traits, but some genes do control the development of the nervous system, which in turn controls behavior.

For the purpose of the study, the child's personality is focused on the development of expressive behavior, fine motor skills, cognitive ability and socio – emotional patterns.

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Every child enters kindergarten at a different level and teachers expect a huge variation in the skills each pupil brings. In entering kindergarten some children are in the transition from home to school. Every year at the beginning of the school year teachers and parents encountered different problems in motivating their children, most of the children at this age 5- 6 years old have separation anxiety – crying and clinging to parents at drop off time in school. Kindergarten pupils are likely to have mood swings that teachers and parents should have more patience to understand. Think of techniques and motivational strategies to come up with this situation to develop their kids' varied skills. In addition to gaps in academic skill at kindergarten entry, some pupils are at risk for the development of socioemotional skills.

Maslow (1943, 1954) stated that people are motivated to achieve certain needs and that some needs take precedence over others. Our most basic needs are for physical survival, and this will be the first thing that motivates our behavior. Once that level is fulfilled the next level up is what motivates us and so on.

Eric Ericson (1958, 1963), on the other hand, believes that childhood is very important in personality development. He created a theory of psychosocial development that covers an entire life and that personality develops in a series of stages namely: trust, independence, initiative, accomplishment identity, relationship, contribution and reflection. The psychosocial development theory proposes our personality develops through eight stages, from infancy to old age. He believes that to become fully functional, confident members of society we must successfully complete each stage and resolve two conflicting states.

Self – determination Theory (SDT; Deci & Ryan, 2000), distinguish types of motivation based on the different reasons that give rise to an action. Intrinsic motivation refers to doing something because it is inherently interesting or enjoyable and extrinsic motivation refers to doing something because it leads to repeatable outcome.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to know the motivational ability of teachers and parental involvement in motivation as correlates of personality development among kindergarten pupils. To determine the relationship of teachers' motivational ability and parents' involvement in motivation with personality development among kindergarten pupils.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes the descriptive correlation design which is purposive process of gathering, analyzing, classifying and tabulating data from the answer of teachers and parents of kindergarten pupils. The design used since the purpose of the study is to see if there is a relationship between the variables.

The respondents of this study consisted of the teachers and the parents of the kindergarten pupils in the District of Nagcarlan in the Division of Laguna through purposive sampling technique. (Table 1). Parents' population depends on the number of kindergarten pupils in the respondent schools. The questionnaire made use of the Likert Scale of 1-5 in perceiving the major variables of the study.

The researcher asked permission from the Offices of the District Supervisor and School Principals for the conduct of the study.

After having identified the total number of teachers and parent-respondents, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaire for personal assessment of the problem under study. The teachers and the parents got involved in the mechanics of the study. They were given enough time to accomplish the questionnaire.

Simple descriptive statistics such as frequency count and percent distribution were used to describe the respondents' profile. Perceived motivational ability of the teachers and that of parents' involvement in motivation were assessed using mean and standard deviation. To determine the significant relationship between independent and dependent variables, Pearson Product – Moment Correlation Coefficient was used at 0.01 level of significance for the test of relationship between motivational ability of teacher and that of personality development of kindergarten pupils. The relationship between parents' involvement in motivation and that of personality development of kindergarten pupils at 0.05 level of significance.

Test of Relationship between Variables Correlation between Personality Development of Kindergarten Pupils and Perceived Motivational Ability of the Teacher

The researcher utilized a survey questionnaire in the conduct of the study. The questionnaire is divided into three parts. Part I consists of the personal details of the respondents such as age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, occupation and monthly income. Part

II provides questions regarding motivational ability of teachers and parental involvement in motivation. Part III dwells on the aspects of personality development of the pupils in terms of expressive, fine-motor, cognitive and socio- emotional development.

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Teachers Motivational Ability	Expressive Development	Fine Motor Development	Cognitive Development	Socio-emotional Development
Instructional	.665**	.566**	.754**	.430*
Incentives Teaching Strategies	.644**	.632**	.682**	.484**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Legend: .0 - .2 Very weak relationship .2 - .4 Weak relationship

.4 - .6 Moderate relationship .6 - .8 Strong relationship

.8 - 1.0 Very strong relationship

Testing the significant relationship between personality development of kindergarten pupils and the perceived motivational ability as to teacher-respondents is shown. Based on the result of the study, there is a significant relationship shown between instructional incentives to

expressive development (r=0.665), fine motor development (r=0.566), cognitive development (r=0.754), and socio-emotional development (r=0.430). Moreover, there is a significant relationship shown between teaching strategies to expressive development (r=0.644), fine motor development (r=0.632), cognitive development (r=0.682), and socio-emotional development (r=0.484).

motor development and cognitive development. Moreover, there is no significant relationship between social interaction to expressive development, cognitive development, and socio-emotional development while there is a significant relationship in social interaction and fine motor development. Therefore, the hypothesis is partially supported.

The following recommendations are

Parents' Involvement in Motivation	Personality Development of Pupils			
	Expressive Development	Fine Motor Development	Cognitive Development	Socio-emotional Development
Motivational Techniques	0.094	.156*	.152*	0.077
Social Interaction	0.118	.171*	0.09	0.121

Testing the significant relationship between personality development of kindergarten pupils and perceived motivational ability as to parents' involvement in motivational ability was shown in Table 16. Based on the result of the study, there is no significant relationship shown between motivational techniques to expressive development (r=0.094), and socio-emotional development (r=0.077) while there is a significant relationship in motivational techniques to fine motor development (r=0.156) and cognitive development (r=0.152). Moreover, there is no significant relationship shown between social interaction to expressive development

(r=0.118), cognitive development (r=0.09), and socio-emotional development (r=0.121) while there is a significant relationship in social interaction to fine motor development (r=0.171).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The following conclusions are formulated:

1. Personality development of kindergarten pupils is significantly related to the motivational ability of teachers. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not sustained.

2. There is no significant relationship between motivational technique to expressive development and socio-emotional development while there is a significant relationship to fine School head may expand with a longer timeframe and consist of a larger sample size, and with the added perspective from different schools or grade level as well.

1. Future researchers may use other variables to identify the advantages and disadvantages of motivational ability of

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teachers and parents' involvement in motivation in relation to the development of personality among kindergarten pupils in the pre-school setting.

2. Another study that focuses on the challenges faced by teacher and parent respondents towards their motivational ability and aspects of personality development of kindergarten pupils may be conducted.

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